

FIZ Karlsruhe - Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure | Action Plan

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

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Preamble

As FIZ Karlsruhe - Leibniz-Institute for Information Infrastructure, we respect discipline and context-specific practices in research assessment. We aim to apply efficient and effective processes for research assessment while avoiding overburdening researchers with reporting obligations.

At the national level, FIZ Karlsruhe participates in the National Chapter Germany of CoARA with its overarching aim to support the implementation of the research assessment reform in Germany and to function as a forum for the discussion and coordination of CoARA matters specific to the German research landscape.

As a member of the Leibniz Association, in which activities related to research assessment within and outside the Leibniz Association are being steered via the Leibniz Strategy Forum on Research Assessment, FIZ Karlsruhe receives “impulses from internal reflection processes to be incorporated into the reform process at European level and, vice versa, impulses from the European discussion to be incorporated into the internal reflection processes”¹.

FIZ Karlsruhe also signed the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information² and participates in the related working groups “Evaluating Open Data” and “Sustaining Infrastructures”.

In our current process of implementing the Core Commitments of the CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, we focus on five areas:

1. Cooperation in the German Competence Network for Bibliometrics

As a data and technology provider and the elected consortial co-lead (Wolfram Horstmann) in the German Competence Network Bibliometrics (KB)³, we engage in (open) bibliometric data and responsible use of bibliometric indicators and methods, where we as FIZ Karlsruhe also provide support to users in understanding and using the data.

A key GOAL is to build open and sustainable infrastructure for open, enriched and quality assured bibliometric data for the German research community in science and technologies. This will allow the engagement for full transparency and opportunities for self training and skills development in the application of research assessment (competence building supported by infrastructure).

In the coming 2-5 years, we plan together with our partners to:

- continue the migration towards open bibliometric data,
- set up quality assurance processes on open bibliometric databases of the KB,
- continue work on the curation and enrichment of data and the disambiguation of entities, like the German institutions,

¹ CoARA Action Plan by the Leibniz Association, Status as of 04 October 2024, DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13774319](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13774319))

² <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

³ <https://bibliometrie.info/>

- set up a competence building platform to support an informed and correct use of bibliometric data for research assessment.

2. Subject-specific Services and Quality Controlled Research Metadata

We support the informed and responsible assessment of research by subject-specific domain experts, specifically as the host of the global information platform for Mathematics, zbMATH Open⁴. We support these activities by filtering research output according to subject-specific quality criteria. In addition, we support researchers in evaluating individual research outputs. Moreover, we provide tools and processes to detect misuse and gaming of academic publishing outlets and aggregation services, including our infrastructure.

With this, our GOAL is to provide a platform of quality-assured data, including the engagement of the respective communities worldwide and quality assurance of research outputs post publication.

In the coming 2-5 years, we plan to

- raise awareness of the misuse of quantitative indicators,
- facilitate data literacy and data analytics competences for a responsible use of our services,
- develop tools and processes that help to unmask malicious publication behaviour.

3. National and International Alignment

We engage in the expansion of the evaluation practice of research in the sense of Open Science: eResearch, research data, networking with open information platforms such as the National Data Infrastructure in Germany NFDI⁵, the European Open Science Cloud EOSC⁶, OpenAIRE⁷, and the Research Data Alliance RDA⁸.

In this area of engagement, our GOAL is to support dialogue and discourse on research assessment in current and large research infrastructure environments/ecologies.

In the coming 2-5 years, we plan to connect the discourses in the Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie Germany and the NFDI with possible implications at the international level. Concrete steps to align our activities are currently being prepared in cooperation with OpenAIRE.

4. Relevant Research and Outreach for Research Assessment

We foster research on the further development of research assessment practices. In the context of Mathematics and information infrastructure, regular publications⁹ on scientometric aspects are being produced. Additionally, two current PhD projects under the

⁴ <https://zbmath.org/>

⁵ <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

⁶ <https://eosc.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁹ <https://www.fiz-karlsruhe.de/en/forschung/publikationen-0>

supervision of Wolfram Horstmann (as Professor at the Institute of Library and Information Science at the Humboldt University of Berlin) address relevant aspects: first, the development, validity of data and critical analyses on Open Access transformation processes is addressed in a and, second, the impact of Open Science Policy at CERN, also with respect to the career relevance of Open Data, Open Software and Open Hardware is addressed in a PhD at CERN on the basis of a Gentner Scholarship. In addition, regular Master-theses on topics are supervised and research assessment is pro-actively addressed through participation in panels and committees in Science Policy.

In the coming 2-5 years, we plan to continue to foster related research through PhDs and Master-theses, further publish and participate in the science policy discourse.

5. Reforming processes in the recruitment, performance evaluation and career progression of academic staff

For our internal processes, we reinforce and promote qualitative research assessment criteria in our recruitment, performance evaluation and career progression processes of academic staff. In this respect, we include multiple perspectives and reduce potential biases in the evaluation processes for hiring and promotion of our academic staff. We consider a variety of academic achievements and outcomes in our assessments. In line with our Open Access policy we acknowledge and promote open access practices and open source developments.

Our GOAL is to systematically integrate more opportunities and activities for leadership training and the development of additional competencies of academic staff in our personnel development practices. The same applies for our recruitment process where we will scale up and formalise good practices in view of a differentiated approach for recruiting, hiring and promoting researchers.

In the coming 2-5 years, we plan to systematically integrate and foster the already initiated as well as new approaches with regards to more balanced, multi-dimensional and non-biased recruitment and career development processes.